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Report of the Informatics Europe Working Group on:

Ethical/Social Impact of Informatics as a Study Subject in Informatics University Degree Programs

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with contribution from the
Working Group Members

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- *Informatics Education in Europe: Institutions, Degrees, Students, Positions, Salaries. Key Data 2008-2013* (2014, Cristina Pereira, Bertrand Meyer, Enrico Nardelli, Hannes Werthner).
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ABOUT THIS REPORT

Information technology (IT) is constantly developing, influencing our everyday life, and impacting choices and decisions at individual as well as at collective level. Thus, IT is invading the social, political and economic spheres. Systems and tools that use modern computer science technologies have clear ethical and social impacts. Even if such impacts have already been subject of discussion in the Artificial Intelligence field, their scope is definitely much broader, and they potentially affect all the fields of Informatics. What happens when they control autonomous systems or make important decisions? How should they be developed and deployed? Can they be made predictable and reliable? Which ethical and legal implications should be observed? The social and ethical impact of new technologies is a key issue of our increasingly connected society that affects users, developers, researchers and governments.

During their training in university degree programs in Informatics, students are provided with the basis for designing and developing modern computer systems. A question arises, then, if they should be trained also on ethical and societal topics, thus enabling them to conceive “good” and beneficial Informatics systems for the society. In 2019 a group of experts, following an open call for interest disseminated in Europe, was convened with the goal of analyze this issue. The working group on **“Ethical/social impact of Informatics as a study subject in Informatics university degree programs”** has tried to understand the current state of affairs and to solicit a discussion on these topics, by answering questions such as, for example: Should ethical/social impact of Informatics be a study subject in Informatics university degree programs? Why? What are the main ethical issues arising from the application of Informatics in society? In which areas ethical/social impacts of Informatics are more evident? Which topics of study at university programs should be taught to make students skilled in ethics-aware design?

This report is the first product of the activity of this working group, outlining the possible approaches, the state of the art, and suggestions and guidelines for inclusion of topics related to ethics, responsibility and social impacts in Informatics university degree programs.

Given the broadness of the topic, in this first exploratory phase, we surveyed the position of the WG members. We have had an enthusiastic participation: 30 out of 32 WG members replied to the questionnaire. In this report, we collect and summarize the results of this consultation together with feedbacks and comments from WG members, to provide a first starting point for further discussions and to establish how to focus and organize further work of the WG.

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¹ Idoia Ana Salazar Garcia joined the WG after the survey.

1. Executive Summary

In this report, we collect and summarize in data and figures the results of this consultation together with feedbacks and comments from WG.

This collected material is a first step towards a more deep and informed discussion about the topic of **if and how ethical/social impact of Informatics should be a study subject in Informatics university degree programs**. Notice that this does not necessarily imply that ethics or social impact should be a study subject, but asks whether the study of ethics or social impact should be present in some way in the degree programs.

Some points (possibly subjects of further investigations) emerged from this consultation and can be summarized as follows:

- **Several members of the WG have proven experiences** in the development, implementation, and monitoring of courses about ethics and social impact in the different level degree programs of the ICT area. Most of them have a specific background in Computer Science and Engineering, Mathematics, Logic, Ethics and Philosophy (of Science and Technology), Education, Sociology and Law. Some of them have a highly interdisciplinary profile covering both Computer Science & Engineering, and Philosophy.
- WG members have great interest in these subjects, as foreseeable. Almost all respondents pointed out the risks and perspectives of the implementation of the newest applications of Informatics. The areas of Informatics considered to have the **greatest impact** from this point of view are Artificial Intelligence and Autonomous Intelligent Systems (e.g. Autonomous Vehicles), Machine Learning, Cryptology, Security, Privacy, Human Computer Interaction and Bioinformatics.
- For the most part, the answers are **positive** to the question: “Should the ethical/social impact of Informatics be a study subject in Informatics university degree programs?” The result seems obvious, possibly due both to the specific skills of the respondents and their interest in participating in the WG on these issues. In general, **the motivations are well articulated and consistent**.
The importance of teaching ethics and social impact is recognized as important also in the case of negative responses. However, such answers concern the fact that ethical/social impact of Informatics is not yet considered a clear intellectual discipline, and therefore it should be incorporated into several technical subjects, so that students perceive them as a part of their discipline.
- With respect to the topics that should be taught, some suggestions are more methodological, others are more specific about courses contents.
The report also classifies the topics to be emphasized in relation to the social and ethical impact with respect to the different areas of Informatics. The classification can be a useful guide to better link the teaching of ethical/social aspects with the appropriate technological subjects.

- The majority of the answers suggest that **social and ethical aspects of Informatics could be taught in the context of Bachelor programs** and that these courses should be mandatory. With respect to who should teach these courses/modules, the majority of the respondents wish a close collaboration between different teachers, with different backgrounds.
- A (preliminary) list of some existing courses within Informatics university degree programs which address ethical/social impacts of Informatics, has been collected through the feedback of the respondents. The list testifies that this topic is already a well-developed academic field, with accredited institutions training huge numbers of students for Bachelor, Master and PhD degrees. However, this list is to be intended just as an example of what is currently happening and a starting point for further investigation.

The report is organized in three distinct but related sections:

- Section 2 focuses on the participants and their professional profile.
- Section 3 is the core of the survey, and deals with the ethical/social impact of Informatics as a study subject in Informatics university degree programs.
- Section 4 collects suggested documentation.

2. Presentation of the participants

In this section and the following ones a summary of the answers² is presented. Questions are presented in bold font. Comments of the respondents, when relevant, have been reported, and presented in italics with a smaller font size and smaller paragraph width.

All WG members are working at Universities of several European countries.

Table 1. Type of organization

	<i>Count</i>	<i>%</i>
University	29	96,7%
Government and University	1	3,3%

Position: 26 out of 30 participants are currently holding a position as a University Professor.

2.1. Skills related to the topic of the Working Group

Several members of the WG have proven experiences in the development, implementation, and monitoring of courses about ethics and social impact in the different level degree programs of the ICT area. In particular, most of them have a direct experience in teaching ethics to students of the ICT area, and of Computer Science and Engineering in particular:

- Ethics in Computer Science,
- Ethics and ICT,
- Social, Professional and Ethical Aspects of IT,
- Computer Ethics,
- Ethics of AI,

² A file containing the raw data in .CSV format for all survey answers can be found at this link: <https://www.informatics-europe.org/images/documents/WG-Ethics-Questionnaires.csv>

- Ethics contents in AI and Data Science courses,
- Ethics and Legislation,
- Research Ethics.

With respect to specific skills, most of them have a specific background in Computer Science and Engineering, Mathematics, Logic, Ethics and Philosophy (of Science and Technology), Education, Sociology and Law. Some of them have a highly interdisciplinary profile covering both Computer Science & Engineering, and Philosophy.

With respect to their specific area of interest (in which they do research activities) we can mention:

AI, Argumentation, Big Data Analytics, Big Data Management, Bioinformatics, Computable Logic, Computer Law, Cyber Security, Data Mining, Data Science, Education, Ethics, Ethics in Biomedical Research and Computer Science, Free and Open-Source Software, IoT, Machine Learning, Managing Relationships and Team Working, Metadata Management, Privacy, Security, Social Media, Software Engineering, Statistics, Web Technologies and E-learning.

Most of them are interested in the intersection between the technical and social aspects of technology.

The basic areas of expertise of the responders can be quantitatively summarized as follows (where Others also includes, e.g., Statistics, Philosophy, and Mathematics):

Table 2. Area of expertise

	<i>Count</i>	<i>%</i>
Informatics	25	33,3%
Ethics	18	24,0%
Education	18	24,0%
Social Sciences	4	5,3%
Government	2	2,7%
Law	2	2,7%
Psychology	1	1,3%
Others	5	6,7%

2.2. Why are you interested in this topic?

Some members have a long-standing interest in this topic. Motivations that drive WG experts to work on this topic are very different. They are related to a general interest for this issue that is conceived as important by itself for its social concern: *“The future of Computer Science it will be ethical or it will not be”, “The development of AI systems, as well as any technology, should be driven by ethical principles and analyze its consequences in society and sustainability”*.

Personal considerations have been provided too. For instance, ethics and social impact are already part of respondents’ research, teaching and institutional activities, or respondents are planning a course or a lecture on these topics.

A member of the WG, for instance, accepted a chair for Philosophy and History of Science with the task to build up a centre which should provide philosophical reflections on ongoing research in Machine Learning. Another is a member of the Scientific Council of the Centre of Bioethics and Social Studies and a member of their university Ethics in Scientific Research Commission. Several WG members are chairs or members of their university Ethics Committees or Boards in Computer Science, one is the Vice Chair of the European Commission High-Level Expert Group on AI.

3. Ethical/social impact of Informatics as a study subject in Informatics university degree programs

3.1. Which are the main ethical/social issues arising from the application of Informatics in the society?

WG members have a great interest in these subjects and, as foreseeable, many articulated and precise answers and statements have been provided in the survey. Some of the most representative answers are summarized in the following.

"Informatics transforms the society in unexpected ways. Especially relevant are the consequences on new generations, who have born with smart phones and all current advancements."

"Ethics deals with the principles of right and wrong that individuals, acting as free moral agents, use to make choices to guide their behaviors."

"Information Systems raise new ethical questions because they create opportunities for intense social change, threatening existing distributions of power, money, rights, and obligations and new kinds of crime."

"Very relevant is the inclusiveness of the technology, how can it arrive to all, and how can contribute to better integrate specific collectives (e.g., people with functional diversity, low income population, etc.)."

"We have to avoid the creation of a divide between entities having access to huge amount of data about everyone, and computational power to make use of it, and the rest of the world."

"Limited access to data, internet, resources and applications can create new digital divides."

Almost all respondents point out the risks related to the implementation of the newest applications of Informatics.

"The application of Informatics should be seen to bring benefit. There are dangers arising from cyber violations, loss of privacy both of individuals and organizations, automation, loss of property, inappropriate reuse of the work of others."

"With advances in Artificial Intelligence there are serious issues associated with the future of work."

"There are issues related to the impact of Informatics on fundamental human rights, through impacting privacy, agency, and freedom."

"There is a great potential for manipulation of people using information tools."

Concerns are raised also on the process of developing software tools:

"In the automation of numerous processes that previously required human interaction, we have to avoid putting the architecture of the interaction process in the hands of distant programmers instead of local people."

"The computer programs (algorithms) are used to make decisions, but the person that applies the decision does not know how the program (algorithm) works. In addition, the programmer does not foresee the consequences."

As expected, Machine Learning, and Autonomy of the Systems, have raised concerns as well:

"A particular challenge is the lack of explanatory structure in decisions made by "black box" technologies applied in Machine Learning."

"Machine Learning systems are often described and deployed inappropriately."

"Autonomous decision making can abuse of technology for proper gains (criminality, abuse of power, ...). Always decisions made by machines are non-accountable/verifiable."

Some provided an answer in terms of suggested keywords related to this question:

"Surveillance, blind trust in numbers, bias, security, legal issues, intellectual property, control of information, democratic values, mass media, e-government (especially e-elections), manipulation of preferences and opinions, accessibility (for disabled people)."

"Data privacy, informed consent, issues related to IoT, responsible conduct of research, bioinformatics, control over workers, unfairness and discrimination, unemployment and workers' rights."

"Cybersecurity in society, recognizing bias in AI, ethics in an information society, responsibility, accountability, liability, autonomous decision making, transparency, distribution of responsibility, control of internet (censorship, loss of neutrality, loss of autonomy)."

"Wearables implants, biotechnology artifacts."

3.2. In which areas ethical/social impact of Informatics is more evident?

In this subsection we present and discuss a table where each ERC PE6 area is rated with its importance with respect to the ethical/social impact, according to the respondents. We have chosen ERC PE6 classification for its obvious advantage of allowing us to place our considerations in the context of an existing and well establish framework. Of course, this choice has also some disadvantages. For example a respondent noticed that: *"The choice of PE6 classification as reference is a little one-sided, as various issues (e.g. the ones that should be addressed by psychology or law specialists) seem to be not covered. Right now, the list reflects a classical computer science point of view"*. An objective for the continuation of work in this area will necessarily be to revise and improve it, maybe adding new elements such as business models, legal issues (patents, licences, copyright), (social) media.

The PE6 areas considered to have the **greatest impact** from this point of view are, in decreasing order of importance:

1. PE6_7 Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Systems, Multi Agent Systems
2. PE6_11 Machine Learning, Statistical Data Processing and Applications using Signal Processing (e.g. Speech, Image, Video)
3. PE6_5 Cryptology, Security, Privacy, Quantum Crypto
4. PE6_9 Human Computer Interaction and Interface, Visualization and Natural Language Processing
5. PE6_13 Bioinformatics, Biocomputing, and DNA and Molecular Computation
6. PE6_10 Web and Information Systems, Database Systems, Information Retrieval and Digital Libraries, Data Fusion

The PE6 areas considered to have the **least impact** from this point of view are, in increasing order:

1. PE6_4 Theoretical Computer Science, Formal Methods, and Quantum Computing
2. PE6_12 Scientific Computing, Simulation and Modelling Tools
3. PE6_3 Software Engineering, Operating Systems, Computer Languages.

It has been pointed out by some members of the WG that considering the most "foundational" areas as less relevant for the ethical / social impact can be misleading because it is precisely through these foundations that a computer system can be designed in a socially responsible way. As everyone now speaks of "privacy by design" or "security by design" we should talk about "socially responsible by design" and to do this we need to inject this dimension into the foundational areas such as Software Engineering with an importance similar to Security and Privacy.

Table 3. In which areas ethical/social impact of Informatics is more evident?

	<i>count</i>			<i>%</i>		
	low	medium	high	low	medium	high
PE6_1 Computer Architecture, Pervasive Computing, Ubiquitous Computing	4	13	13	13,3%	43,3%	43,3%
PE6_2 Computer Systems, Parallel/Distributed Systems, Sensor Networks, Embedded Systems, Cyber-Physical Systems	1	14	13	3,6%	50,0%	46,4%
PE6_3 Software Engineering, Operating Systems, Computer Languages	11	10	8	37,9%	34,5%	27,6%
PE6_4 Theoretical Computer Science, Formal Methods, and Quantum Computing	15	11	3	51,7%	37,9%	10,3%
PE6_5 Cryptology, Security, Privacy, Quantum Crypto	0	7	23	0%	23,3%	76,7%
PE6_6 Algorithms, Distributed, Parallel and Network Algorithms, Algorithmic Game Theory	8	12	9	27,6%	41,4%	31,0%
PE6_7 Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Systems, Multi Agent Systems	0	0	30	0%	0%	100%
PE6_8 Computer Graphics, Computer Vision, Multimedia, Computer Games	2	18	9	6,9%	62,1%	31,0%
PE6_9 Human Computer Interaction and Interface, Visualisation and Natural Language Processing	2	6	22	6,7%	20,0%	73,3%
PE6_10 Web and Information Systems, Database Systems, Information Retrieval and Digital Libraries, Data Fusion	1	11	18	3,3%	36,7%	60,0%
PE6_11 Machine Learning, Statistical Data Processing and Applications using Signal Processing (e.g. Speech, Image, Video)	0	4	26	0%	13,3%	86,7%
PE6_12 Scientific Computing, Simulation and Modelling Tools	13	13	3	44,8%	44,8%	10,3%
PE6_13 Bioinformatics, Biocomputing, and DNA and Molecular Computation	2	8	19	6,9%	27,6%	65,5%

Table 3 graph: In which areas ethical/social impact of Informatics is more evident?

3.3. Should the ethical/social impact of Informatics be a study subject in Informatics university degree programs?

As shown in the following table, 90% of the answers were positive to the question. The result seems obvious, and possibly due both to the specific skills of the respondents and to their interest in participating in the WG on these issues.

Table 4. Should the ethical/social impact of Informatics be a study subject in Informatics university degree programs?

	<i>count</i>	<i>%</i>
yes	27	90%
no	3	10%

The importance of teaching ethics and social impact is recognized as important also in the case of **negative responses**. These derived from the concern that ethical/social impact of Informatics is not considered yet a clear intellectual discipline and therefore it should be taught as part of other programs. It was argued that if ethical/social impact of Informatics is studied as a distinct subject there is a risk that the students will not relate them to their studies. Instead, ethics and social aspects should be incorporated into several technical subjects, so that students perceive them as a part of their discipline. It should be part of the main literacy and should be included in the life-long learning topics, as well as part of the courses at school. Some respondents have noticed that the question itself could be interpreted as assuming that ethics should be studied as a separate subject. On the basis of this feedback a better formulation of the question could indeed have been: "Should the ethical / social impact of Informatics be studied in Informatics university degree programs?" This observation might also provide a motivation behind the negative answers, not because they think that ethics/social impact should not be studied within Informatics degree programs, but because they believe that it should not be studied as a distinct subject.

3.4. Why should the ethical/social impact of Informatics be a study subject in Informatics university degree programs?

This question was posed only to those who answered positively to the previous one.

We report below some of the provided motivations. Most of the answers are rooted on very similar arguments, even if expressed in different ways and with different emphasis. In general, the motivational framework is consistent.

"First for professional responsibility of the future professionals working in programming. In addition, the impact of the decisions made by programmers when modeling the world and its decisions is increasingly evident, affects a greater number of people and moves towards the widening of the digital divide."

"It is simply naive to assume that Informatics skills are neutral to ethical and social impact they can have - remember "Cambridge Analytica"."

"Informatics students (and teachers) should be able to reflect on ethical/societal challenges. You can't leave that to ill-informed philosophers! Plus: Philosophers need an incentive to really understand what is going on in Computer Science."

“Having taught my course for years, it has had many good effects - besides the direct knowledge and awareness of ethical issues, it has also been a good way to introduce more generic skills (academic writing and discussion, group-work, presentation skills etc.).”

“This is a classic vital 'background' area in the tech education that, at the end, differentiates between a professional and a 'code monkey'.”

“Because it is in all other Engineering subjects. One cannot rely on non-experts to judge the ethical implications of systems they do not understand.”

“Usually the students are not familiar with ethical issues, in particular related to Informatics field.”

“Providing future computer experts with awareness of social and legal issues; support the development of socially beneficial application; prevention of risks.”

“In our University it is a mandatory subject of study and students appreciate. It is oriented to promote a critical analysis on different issues that concern ethics and legal implications of Informatics.”

“Future professionals in Computer Science and Engineering should be aware that the technologies that they design are not neutral and impact in a very strong way on people and society. Moreover, they have to be aware that some ethical issues arise already at the level of design and have to be considered at the beginning of the design phase to orient the design itself.”

“Reflection of responsibility. Informatics has an impact on society, and students should be able to recognize that.”

“Because every student should be aware of ethics so that they behave in a more ethical way later in their profession. The lack of ethical behaviour is a large part of what is wrong in this world. The more students are confronted with ethics, the more they will be aware of what it is, and hopefully behave ethically.”

“Computer scientists and engineers cannot ignore the impact of their work on society. If they are simply concerned with the technical aspect of their work, then they behave like “intelligent instruments” in the hands of others; they get then depersonalized.”

“Students must be made aware that they are privileged to work in such an important area but that they have an ethical responsibility to behave in a manner that reflects well on the discipline.”

“Our lives depend on them, e.g. an IA system will determine if we are employable or not or if we will probably become depressed or a criminal in a few months. Our attention is now becoming a commercial asset, as well as our private personal data. IT artifacts integrated in human bodies may significantly transform our human behavior, from increasing discrimination to enhancing control means.”

“To make them aware of the risks for our society underlying the software and the hardware that they develop.”

“Because I think we should educate to social responsibility whenever the discipline thought is likely to have an impact of humans and the quality of their lives. It is not a case that the ACM has redacted its Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct for all computing professionals.”

“Students will face ethical dilemmas in the workplace, whatever form their future career takes. They need help in recognizing when this happens, and what to do about it when it does.”

“My perspective is one of social shaping between society and technology. As such, those developing the tools have a major influence in the final form the artefacts have.”

"Informatics is fundamental to the data economy and how information technology is used to influence human behaviour."

"It is both all over the news, and often unnoticed by the computer scientist designing a system. Teaching such a class increases awareness and offers tools that help students to have an informed reaction to news coverage."

3.5. Which are the topics of study that should be taught at university courses in order to make students skilled in ethically aligned design/responsible design?

Some of the answers to this question are listed below. Some suggestions are more methodological, others provide more specific indications regarding the topics that should be addressed. Overall, the answers offer an interesting overview that can be considered a starting point for subsequent discussions.

Methodological considerations:

"The subject should fit the students' subjects. I favor integrating ethics and social sciences in other courses. A general introduction might be useful, though."

"The social/ethical issues are much wider than just design."

"This is hard, as there isn't yet a well-developed theory (at least not in Europe: the US has had work for a long time on implicit racial bias). There are certainly case studies that can be considered (Facebook advertising, Amazon hiring, NY taxicab data, UK car insurance)."

"Areas included in codes of ethics such as the new ACM code of ethics and professional practice. In addition students should be aware of the legal frameworks as well as the importance of keeping up to date; related competence frameworks, accreditation issues, the role of professional bodies may also be included. Importantly students should also gain experience of applying their knowledge of ethics."

"Digital rights, which include all the topics mentioned (privacy, freedom, transparency of design/use, biases in IT systems, persuasion ...). An "ethics by design" approach, as most students at the beginning of the course declare that the responsibility relies on users and regulators and rarely identify designers' responsibility and deny the "artifact have politics" premise."

"General aspects of the social and personal responsibility of scientists; specific examples of how these arise in practice in Informatics."

"Social construction of technology, mutual shaping of technology, datafication or processes of online identity, among others."

"No specific topic. I think the focus is on teaching how to identify an ethical question and how to find a way to take a position about it."

Suggested Topics:

"Privacy. Surveillance. Social networks. Cryptography. Digital rights. Online communities. Freedom of expression a censorship in internet. Anonymity. Transparency. Net Neutrality. Privileges, inequality and Digital divide. Gender gap. Software design bias. Copyright: Licenses, free software and free hardware."

"Historical examples where Informatics had unexpected impact, from "Enigma" to "Cambridge Analytica", responsibility coming with privacy and cryptography, (lack of) explanatory structure in computer generated "answers"."

“Scientific research and ethics; Definitions, theories and ethical principles; The ethical decision-making process; Ethical issues related to the authorship; Publications and the peer review process; Deviations in the management of scientific research; Intellectual property; Ethical and legal rules related to the Internet, Data privacy.”

“Foundations of ethics, legal principles and basics of computer law, ethics of computer design, machine ethics, machine law.”

“Inclusiveness and design for all. Sustainability. Accessibility and assistive technologies. Privacy and security. Algorithm and data bias.”

“Introduction to ethics, critical thinking, responsibility, privacy, discrimination, security, ethics and data analytics, ethics and gaming, intellectual property, artificial intelligence.”

“Computer ethics, Critical thinking, History of computer science and engineering.”

“Stakeholder analysis, Impact assessment.”

“Information rights and obligations, Property rights and obligations, Accountability and control, Due process, Golden Rule, Do unto others as you would have them do unto you, Utilitarian Principle: take the action that achieves the higher or greater value, Risk Aversion Principle: take the action that produces the least harm or least potential cost Ethical “no free lunch” rule.”

“Methods and tools for data protection, confidentiality; Risk detection and mitigation measures; Fairness acting; Software design aligned to ethical requirements.”

“Fundamentals of ethics: freedom and responsibility, moral values and moral judgment, autonomy, ethical reason vs scientific and technical reason, ethics and law, codes of ethical conduct.”

“Artificial Intelligence responsibilities, Social media and software programs problems: security, fake news, privacy.”

“Management of sensible data and GDPR.”

“Ethics in Computer Science, privacy, data management, personal/public limit, fake, spam, social media biases, cybersecurity issues, trust, confidence.”

“History of ethics and philosophy of science; Research Design and Scientific Method; Data science ethics (privacy, anonymity, data validity, etc.); The Code (ACM); Human Rights and the Internet (e.g., Snowden, Wikileaks); Social Responsibility of Informatics (e.g., Rogaway, The Moral Character of Cryptographic Work); Algorithmic fairness; Robot ethics and AI.”

“Ethics; Law of Information Technology; Privacy Law.”

“Social construction of technology, mutual shaping of technology, datafication or processes of online identity, among others.”

3.6. For each PE6 area please indicate the specific related ethical / social aspects to be addressed

The following table classifies the topics to be emphasized in relation to the social and ethical impact with respect to the different areas of Informatics. This classification can be a useful guide to better link the teaching of ethical/social aspects with the appropriate technological subjects.

Table 5. Specific ethical / social aspects to be addressed to each PE6 area

For each PE6 area please indicate the specific related ethical / social aspects to be addressed						
PE6_1 Computer Architecture, Pervasive Computing, Ubiquitous Computing	PE6_2 Computer Systems, Parallel/ Distributed Systems, Sensor Networks, Embedded Systems, Cyber-Physical Systems	PE6_3 Software Engineering, Operating Systems, Computer Languages	PE6_4 Theoretical Computer Science, Formal Methods, and Quantum Computing	PE6_5 Cryptology, Security, Privacy, Quantum Crypto	PE6_6 Algorithms, Distributed, Parallel and Network Algorithms, Algorithmic Game Theory	PE6_7 Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Systems, Multi Agent Systems
	Surveillance	License		Anonymity, transparency, surveillance	Software design bias	Gender gap, software design bias, transparency
n/a	n/a	The programmer's control over what is actually happening in a software package	Theoretical background to address the questions in the areas	Privacy; (lack of) control over encrypted data - should terrorists have arbitrary cryptographic control?	The programmer's control over what is actually happening in an algorithm	(Lack of) explanatory structure in AI
Ubiquitous surveillance, data ownership, privacy	Risk / Safety, responsibility, surveillance	Fairness and bias	Fairness and bias; anticipating future challenges (especially quantum computing)	Value conflicts in security; power differences (e.g., who decides about what makes a risk?)	Responsibility, trust in game theory	Responsibility of engineers for autonomous systems
Avoiding lock-in in architecture, various ubi-comp issues (e.g. global scale)	Security and privacy (IoT)	Open models, avoiding lock-in, multi-platform systems	Security and privacy	The ethical issues of the theoretical (crypto) and practical end (sec/priv) are completely different	Avoiding the 'ivory tower' (e.g. in practical use of algorithms in medical and judicial applications) and 'black box' marketing	A very wide circle of ethical questions (some are existential for mankind)
The sensitivity of location data (NY taxicab example)	The sensitivity of sensor data and the data collected by embedded systems	The need for secure programming (SQL injection, password handling, etc.)		Ethical implications of security and privacy, especially for the weak/children		Ethical implications of pattern recognition, perpetuation of biases/stereotypes (Google translate example)
Ethics in research, data privacy	Issues related to IoT, data privacy	Only issue related to use of personal data	Research ethics	Data privacy, research ethics	Data privacy, research ethics	Data privacy, research ethics
Security	Legal/ethical issues of surveillance	Transparency/explicability		Surveillance, privacy		Explicability, fairness as applied to algorithms, non-discrimination
Pervasive and ubiquitous computing means that everywhere there is a computing device doing something	Similar to PE6_1, and observation and monitoring of our activities	The development process should integrate different stakeholders, not only engineers.	No critical issue	Privacy concerns. Who has access to what?	Algorithm bias	Transparent autonomy: how to explain why the system takes a decision
Privacy, impact on society	Security, privacy	Security, bias		Security, privacy	Bias/discrimination, security, privacy	AI
Data				Privacy		White box algorithms
Impact of ubiquitous computing on society	Possibility of harm from systems, privacy, impact assessment		Effects of quantum computing on security, impact analysis	Being able to assess impact of security on stakeholders	Availability of computing	Recognising bias, stakeholder analysis, societal impact of applications of AI
Information rights and obligations	Information rights and obligations	Property rights and obligations	Accountability and control	Accountability and control	Accountability and control	Accountability and control
Security risks leading to ethical issues	Security risks leading to ethical issues	Robust programs design			Negotiation rules	Software agents ethical / social behaviour
	Freedom and responsibility		Ethical reason vs scientific and technical reason	Moral values and moral judgment, autonomy	Ethics and law, codes of ethical conduct	Freedom and responsibility, moral values and moral judgment, autonomy, ethical reason vs scientific and technical reason, ethics and law, codes of ethical conduct
Role of hardware in supporting cryptography	Sensors and information gathering. Reduced protection in Internet of Things devices	Dangerous code within libraries. Plagiarism issues. Need to take special steps for critical code. The role of adhering to standards to guard against charges of bad practice, e.g. for safety critical applications	Theoretical methods important but never foolproof	Usual steps important but cocktail of methods desirable in case of compromise	Bias in algorithms. Ownership!	Dangers of automation. Where does responsibility lie? Provision of explanations for decisions
Privacy, security	Privacy, security	Privacy, security		Privacy, security	Privacy, security	Responsibilities, ethical/human aspects
Protection of personal data, GDPR	Protection of personal data, GDPR	Security breaches in software applications	Possible future break of cryptographic codes	Possible future break of cryptographic codes		Security of AI systems, ethics in automated decision making
Privacy	Algorithmic transparency / privacy/ security	Algorithmic transparency	Social responsibility of Informatics research	Dual use of cryptographic work	Algorithmic transparency	Roboethics, and AI
Privacy; transparency/fairness; policy	Privacy; transparency/fairness; policy			Privacy		Privacy; transparency/fairness; policy
Information technology as a tool of surveillance. Impact of technology on privacy and agency	Information technology as a tool of surveillance. Impact of technology on privacy and agency	Information technology as a tool of surveillance. Impact of technology on privacy and agency	Information technology as a tool of surveillance. Impact of technology on privacy and agency	Privacy	Algorithmic bias. Impact on human rights and agency	Algorithmic bias. Impact on human rights and agency
Inclusion/Intrusion of connected devices in all aspects of human life	Associated security and privacy risks	How software development also codifies human life and interactions	What do we learn about what can be done, and cannot be done in computation and communication	New balances of power created by cryptology, impact of changes in perception of privacy in society	What kind of responsibility do I have by designing algorithms/processes in one way or another?	What decisions do I make based on AI, and how to assess its relevance?

For each PE6 area please indicate the specific related ethical / social aspects to be addressed					
PE6_8 Computer Graphics, Computer Vision, Multimedia, Computer Games	PE6_9 Human Computer Interaction and Interface, Visualisation and Natural Language Processing	PE6_10 Web and Information Systems, Database Systems, Information Retrieval and Digital Libraries, Data Fusion	PE6_11 Machine Learning, Statistical Data Processing and Applications using Signal Processing (e.g. Speech, Image, Video)	PE6_12 Scientific Computing, Simulation and Modelling Tools	PE6_13 Bioinformatics, Biocomputing, and DNA and Molecular Computation
Licenses, data protection, privileges, and inequality gender gap	Digital rights, software design bias, privileges and inequality	Digital divide, cryptography, licenses, data protection	Digital divide, software design bias, digital rights, data protections	Software design bias	Digital divide, digital rights
How does the computer generated media world relate to the real world?	Does human work for the computer or the computer for humans?	Responsible use of data	How do you deal with unexplained results from "black box algorithms"?	n/a	What will you do, if you find the "crime gene"?
Exploiting human weaknesses; gamification; inclusive design	Inclusive design, surveillance, bias	Fake news, responsibility, data ownership, privacy	Responsible use of public data, responsible decision making based on ML	Philosophy of Science is much needed here	Anthropology: What is "bio" / "nature"?
Accessibility, simulation issues	Accessibility, user-centered design, language issues	Information freedom, Big Data, data preservation (e.g. Internet Archive)			
	Perpetuation of biases/stereotypes (Google translate example)	Perpetuation of biases/stereotypes (Facebook advertising example)	Ethical implications of pattern recognition, Perpetuation of biases/stereotypes		
Research ethics	Ethical and legal rules related to the Internet, Data privacy	Ethical and legal rules related to the Internet, Data privacy	Data privacy, research ethics	Research ethics, data protection	Research ethics, data protection, data privacy, informed consent, use of biological data
		Access to information, online democracy and manipulation, impacts on work	Issues in stereotyping and discrimination, privacy, surveillance		Bioethics, biolaw
Computer games dependency, like a drug	Emotions management when interacting with a computer	Data and information bias	Lack of transparency in many techniques	Model bias	Interactions with biological systems
Gaming (discrimination, gamers' dilemma, etc.)	Discrimination	Privacy, security, chilling effects, power distribution	Privacy, security, chilling effects, discrimination	Strengths and weaknesses in models and simulation	Privacy, security, chilling effects, discrimination
	Extraction of knowledge		Use of data, data protection		
Informed consent, human subject research	Informed consent, human subject research	Recognising bias, stakeholder analysis, societal impact of applications of AI	Recognising bias, stakeholder analysis, societal impact of applications of AI		Informed consent, human subject research
Information rights and obligations	Accountability and control	Accountability and control	Accountability and control	Information rights and obligations	Accountability and control
Inappropriate content in computer game	Inappropriate content	Data privacy and security	Data confidentiality		Bio-ethics
Moral values and moral judgment, autonomy	Moral values and moral judgment, autonomy	Moral values and moral judgment, autonomy			Freedom and responsibility, moral values and moral judgment, autonomy, ethical reason vs scientific and technical reason, ethics and law, codes of ethical conduct.
Computer vision leads to face recognition, recognition of handwriting, etc. so privacy issues, etc. become relevant	Phishing, compromising the young, bullying, etc. Language translation with all that this entails. Also possibility of building profiles, understanding preferences, tailoring adverts, etc.	Illegal web sites and dangerous material. Students need to understand how to recognise quality sites. One aspect of this is them keeping up to date with best practice	Bias, properly balanced and representative data sets.. Characteristics of high quality data and where to find it. Ethical issues associated with gathering data. Signal processing developments can have an influence on privacy and confidentiality.	Simulations are only simulations and have limitations but can be very valuable	These bring new models of computation and can be used to advantage
Privacy, security	Responsibilities, ethical/human aspects	Responsibilities, ethical/human aspects	Responsibilities, ethical/human aspects	Privacy, security	Privacy, security, responsibilities, ethical/human aspects
Protection of personal data, GDPR		Protection of personal data, GDPR	Discrimination aware data mining, privacy aware data mining		Protection of personal data, GDPR
Usability	Deception, dark patterns, usability security	Transparency, data protection, decision making	Algorithmic transparency, accountability, verifiability	[No opinion]	Privacy
Privacy; transparency/fairness	Privacy; transparency/fairness	Privacy; transparency/fairness; policy	Privacy; transparency/fairness; policy		
Privacy, e.g. facial recognition and surveillance. Impact on human rights and agency	Algorithmic bias. Impact on human rights and agency	Bias. Privacy	Algorithmic bias. Privacy. Impact on human rights and agency	Information technology as a tool of surveillance. Impact of technology on privacy and agency	Algorithmic bias. Privacy. Impact on human rights and agency
What is the impact of virtual worlds on our mental model of our society?	What is the impact of virtual worlds on our mental model of our society?	Associated security and privacy risks	Associated security and privacy risks	What decisions do I make based on those techniques, and how to assess its relevance?	How do these techniques question our perception of ourselves, and how does it modify our world, and for who?

3.7. Practical Issues

The remaining questions of the survey concerned how, from a more practical viewpoint, to teach contents regarding the ethical and social impact of Informatics to students at university. The answers are divided almost equally among those thinking of teaching them (a) in an ad hoc, standalone course; (b) highly integrated in several specific Informatics-related courses; or (c) in a module within a disciplinary course.

Table 6. In which way should the ethical/social impact of Informatics become a subject of study in Informatics university degree programs?

	<i>count</i>	<i>%</i>
Ad hoc, standalone course	9	33,3%
Highly integrated in several specific Informatics-related courses	7	25,9%
A module within a disciplinary course	6	22,2%
Other	5	18,5%

The majority of the answers suggest that social and ethical aspects of Informatics could be taught in the context of Bachelor programs and almost all the answers (85,2%) indicate that these courses should be mandatory. Please remember the previous observation in sub-section 3.3, that some might have interpreted this question as if prescribing ethics/social impact as a distinct subject of study within Informatics degree programs.

Table 7. When should the ethical/social impact of Informatics become a subject of study in Informatics university degree programs?

	<i>count</i>	<i>%</i>
In Bachelor program	14	51,9%
In Master program	6	22,2%
In both Bachelor and Master program	5	18,5%
Other	2	7,4%

Table 7 graph. When should the ethical/social impact of Informatics become a subject of study in Informatics university degree programs?

Table 8. Should a course in ethical/social impact be eligible or mandatory?

	<i>count</i>	<i>%</i>
Mandatory	23	85,2%
Eligible	1	3,7%
Other	3	11,1%

Table 8 graph: Should a course in ethical/social impact be eligible or mandatory?

The motivations for the answer “Other” at the question: “Should a course in the ethical/social impact be eligible or mandatory?” are the following:

“Eligible, but encouraged (need students to be motivated in order to have an impact).”

“Depending on the approach - a generic one should be mandatory.”

“Again it depends on the previous choices.”

With respect to who should teach in these courses/modules, the majority of the respondents (70.4%) wish a close collaboration between different teachers, with different backgrounds.

Table 9. Who should teach in these courses/modules?

	<i>count</i>	<i>%</i>
Collaboration between different teachers, with different backgrounds	19	70,4%
Informatics teachers	4	14,8%
Law teachers	1	3,7%
Other	3	11,1%

When asked about which (type of) teachers should collaborate together, respondents provided the following answers:

“At least, Informatics teachers, Philosophy teachers and Law teachers.”

“Informatics and Philosophy and even Mathematics.”

“Co-teaching Philosophy and Informatics; also: teaching the teachers (Philosophy teaching the Informatics teacher).”

“The more the better. Good generalists can wear several hats, but varying perspectives are always good. A strong component of informatics is needed, as is techno-cultural and historical perspective and understanding of law”.

“It should be mostly led by informatics teachers. There is scope for law lecturers in various areas (privacy especially). Also (not mentioned) social science teachers. My experience of ethics "specialists" has been a failure to understand the need for algorithms, but that may just be my experience.”

“Philosophically-trained ethicists and Informatics teachers should collaborate on these courses.”

“Leading is ethics teachers to teach formal and applied ethics, and to engage students on the ethical implications of their work. Should be supported by Informatics teacher to make the translation from the computer science work to ethical impacts (must have feel for ethics).”

“Psychology for human subject research, informed consent, but also behavioral/decision theory (nudging, bad patterns in UX).”

"CS teachers [+ Ethics teachers] + Law teachers."

"Informatics, ethics, philosophy, law, psychology, religion ..."

"Informatics, ethics and law. Even better if the same teacher is competent in different areas."

"Informatics, ethics, philosophy."

"Informatics, ethics, philosophy, psychology, sociology, social anthropology."

"Informatics, law and ethics teachers would very nicely complement each other."

"Collaboration between teachers of Philosophy, Law and Computer Science."

"Preferably all, in this order: Ethics/Philosophy, Psychology, Informatics and Law."

"Sociologist, psychologists and philosophers, among others."

"Informatics, ethics, law, philosophy, social science, psychology."

"Ethics and philosophy professor with an interest in CS, and CS professor with an interest in ethics."

4. Useful references

In this section we list useful references indicated by individual WG members. It is only for illustrative purpose and does not intend to be exhaustive or complete, given the breadth and the depth of the area. We provide them as a basis for further work producing an annotated reference guide to the field.

4.1. Please provide references to existing courses you know within Informatics university degree programs, which address ethical/social impacts of Informatics (with URLs, when available)

<https://embeddedethics.seas.harvard.edu/module.html>

http://web.fdi.ucm.es/Guia_Docente/Prog_asignatura.asp?fdicurso=2018-2019&titu=39

https://www.etsisi.upm.es/aspectos_sociales_legales_eticos_y_profesionales

<https://www.utwente.nl/en/bms/rests/bachelor-programmes/ti-inf/>

<https://edu.epfl.ch/coursebook/en/global-issues-communication-b-HUM-122-B>

<https://akadeemia.kakupesa.net/arhiiv/SPEAIT2019K/>

<http://www.bath.ac.uk/catalogues/2019-2020/cm/CM10251.html>

<https://marksprevak.com/pdf/teaching/Sprevak---Ethics-of-AI-course-guide.pdf>

http://web.fdi.ucm.es/UCMFiles/pdf/FICHAS_DOCENTES/2018/1488.pdf

<http://home.deib.polimi.it/schiaffo/CE/>

<https://www.inf.uni-hamburg.de/en/inst/ab/eit/teaching.html>

<http://os3.nl/2018-2019/info/ethics>

<https://www.gcu.edu/degree-programs/master-science-health-informatics>

<https://www.fh-krems.ac.at/en/study/bachelor/full-time/informatics/>

<https://uclouvain.be/en-cours-2019-LFSA2202.html>

<https://aplicaciones.uc3m.es/cpa/generaFicha?est=218&anio=2018&plan=256&asig=12749&idioma=1>

<https://www.uniba.it/ricerca/dipartimenti/informatica/didattica/corsi-di-laurea/corsi/sicurezza-informatica-ta/cds-sicurezza-informatica>

<https://www.uniba.it/ricerca/dipartimenti/informatica/didattica/corsi-di-laurea/data-science/data-science>

<https://www.coursera.org/learn/data-science-ethics>

<http://www.inf.ed.ac.uk/teaching/courses/fnlp/lectures/>

<https://www.ucm.es/estudios/grado-ingenieriainformatica-plan-803266>

<https://www.ucm.es/estudios/2018-19/master-ingenieriainformatica-plan-607289>

<http://groups.csail.mit.edu/mac/classes/6.805/>

<https://registrar.princeton.edu/course-offerings/course-details?courseid=012068&term=1194>

<https://cyber.harvard.edu/education>

Data Security and Bioethics, Master program – Bioinformatics, West University of Timisoara (URL not available)

Professional Ethics and Intellectual Property, Vasile Goldis Western University of Arad, Romania (URL not available)

We also note that a cooperative maintained collection of tech ethics curricula can be found at:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jWlrA8jHz5fYAW4h9CkUD8gKS5V98PDJDymRf8d9vKI>

4.2. Further notes about related courses in Europe, provided by respondents

“This subject is mandatory in degree of Computer Science in all universities in Spain.”

“Such courses are essentially mandatory in all UK universities which are BCS accredited, and that is the vast majority of universities. BCS has guidance on social and professional issues.”

“There is a Wiki produced by our students (mostly in Spanish):

https://wikis.fdi.ucm.es/ELP/P%C3%A1gina_principal, also with descriptions from social impact projects that are part of our course. “Human rights in the robot age” Rathenau Instituut report:

<https://www.rathenau.nl/sites/default/files/2018-02/Human%20Rights%20in%20the%20Robot%20Age-Rathenau%20Instituut-2017.pdf>”

4.3. Please provide references to documents, articles and projects you know related to the teaching of ethical/social impacts of Informatics in Informatics university degree programs.

ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct. Available at: <https://www.acm.org/code-of-ethics>

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European Economic and Social Committee. Artificial Intelligence & Society. Available at: <http://www.eesc.europa.eu/?i=portal.en.events-and-activities-artificial-intelligence>

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Guidelines for Researcher on Dual Use and Misuse of Research. Available at: https://www.uhasselt.be/documents/DOC/2017VLIR003_FolderOnderzoek_EN_DEF_20180212.pdf

IEEE Summit on Technology for Health. Available at: <http://ieee-summit.org/>

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4.4. Other suggestions and useful information

"It may be worth looking at documents from accreditation agencies for further material. So BCS, the US bodies (ABET etc.) and the European Informatics Accreditation body EQANIE. There was a move also to include ethical issues in EU competency standards."

"EDINSOST and EDINSOST 2 projects aim at the integration of EDS in university degrees. in particular, in the Bachelor in Informatics Engineering."

"Recently an interest group on Ethics and AI in the Spanish Association for AI (AEPIA) has been created."

"Could be useful having computer scientist in the ethical board of universities. It is educative and help raise awareness of computer science research be subject of an ethical approval."

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